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Comparative Effect of Isokinetic Exercise and Thera Band Strength Training in Patients with Ankle Instability: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Isokinetic Exercise, Thera Band, Strength, Ankle Instability

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function in affected individuals. **Methodology:** This research is used to improve the muscle strength and proprioception (the body's sense of position and movement) to regain better joint control. A randomized controlled trial was focused into two groups: one group is performed isokinetic training using a dynamometer, while the other group is used Thera Bands for progressive resistance exercises during the specific training program. Before and after the training, results such as balance, muscle strength, and functional performance are measured. The purpose of this study is used to identify which method is more effective for restoring ankle stability and avoiding future injuries. The results will help physiotherapists design more practical, affordable, and evidence-based rehabilitation programs, improving recovery and overall quality of life for people who had functional ankle instability.

Results: This study involves 60 participants (mean age 27.03 ± 5.33 years) using non-parametric tests because of non-normal baseline data. Statistically significant within-group improvements demonstrated by the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test for all participants across CAIT, NPRS, Biodex, and SEBT scores post-treatment ($p < 0.01$), shows reduce pain and improve ankle stability and balance. No significant baseline differences except for NPRS were shown by inter-group analysis using the Mann-Whitney Test but post-treatment the Isokinetic group exhibited significantly better results than the Thera Band plus strength group on all measures: Post-CAIT ($p = 0.044$), Post-NPRS ($p = 0.003$), Post-Biodex ($p = 0.008$), and Post-SEBT ($p = 0.001$).

Conclusion: These findings show that while both treatments were effective, isokinetic training resulted in superior enhancement in pain, ankle stability, and dynamic balance.

Background: The repeated ankle sprains, poor balance, lack of strength, and difficulty in daily or sports activities cause ankle instability. Aim: This study shows the combination of isokinetic exercises and Thera Band strength training that maintain ankle stability and

INTRODUCTION:

The most common musculoskeletal problem faced by athletes and active individuals is ankle stability. Repeated ankle sprains sometimes cause chronic condition known as Chronic Ankle Instability (CAI), which is identified by continuous pain, swelling, weakness, and a sense of the ankle “giving way” during movement (1). This instability not only cause limitation in sports and physical activities but it can also disturbed the daily functioning and quality of life (2). Ankle injuries also caused by mechanical laxity, proprioceptive issues and neuromuscular control problem. These degenerative changes are caused by repetitive microtrauma, altered biomechanics, and chronic inflammation, if it not properly managed then it lead to long term disability. The relationship between etiology and pathophysiology in ankle instability creates a self-preserving cycle in which initial ligament injury that leads to structural weakness, which then contributes to neuromuscular impairment and proprioceptive dysfunction, further increasing the risk of reinjury and progressive joint worsen (3).

Traditional management of ankle instability includes therapeutic exercises designed to regain muscle strength, proprioception, and functional stability. Most widely used approaches are isokinetic exercises and elastic resistance (Thera-Band) training. Both methods focus on improving muscular performance and joint stability, but differ in the way resistance is applied and muscle recruitment patterns are trained (4)

Isokinetic training also improve the inversion and eversion. However, Its equipments are very expensive and proper supervision are required in this treatment so it use is limited in rehabilitation centres (5) Chronic ankle instability (CAI), is a multifactorial musculoskeletal condition that mostly develops start from lateral ankle sprain which is characterized by repeated episodes of giving way, continues pain, and functional limitations during weight-bearing and dynamic activities. Ankle instability is caused by acute inversion injuries, which frequently affects the lateral ligament complex of the ankle, including the anterior talofibular ligament (ATFL), calcaneofibular ligament (CFL), and, in severe cases, the posterior talofibular ligament (PTFL). (5) This repeated injury not affected the healing forms of chronic mechanical instability, but it also caused the structural integrity of the ankle joint is compromised, allowing abnormal joint motion and excessive laxity. (6) Most important muscular contributors in ankle stability is the peroneus longus and peroneus brevis, that resist excessive inversion and stabilize the lateral side of the ankle during gait and athletic activities. (7) Biomechanical abnormalities such as increases the foot supination, high medial longitudinal arch (pes cavus), or poor lower limb alignment can also predispose individuals to lateral ankle sprains. (8) Environmental and external factors such as uneven playing surfaces, inappropriate footwear, fatigue, and high-intensity sports participation that can also contribute to the development and persistence of ankle instability. (9)

Abnormal movement contributes to recurrent sprains but it also enhanced degenerative changes within the joint. In addition to mechanical changes, proprioceptive defects play a central role in the persistence of ankle instability. (10) With the time, these neuromuscular problems may become adapted, which cause maladaptation in motor patterns that persist even after tissue healing has occurred. (11) Additionally, chronic inflammation, pain, synovial irritation and effusion in joint limit the range of motion. With the time, persistent instability and abnormal joint loading cause degenerative changes in joint such as cartilage degradation and osteoarthritis. (12) The results could directly inform physiotherapists, sports trainers, and rehabilitation specialists about the most efficient and practical technique for managing ankle instability (13).

Method and Material

This single blinded randomized controlled was conducted in physio rehab center shadrah lahore. which enrolled 60 participants (both male and female) aged 18–35 years with diagnosed functional ankle instability was admitted using a purposive sampling technique and then randomly assign to the two groups (30 participants per group).

Inclusion Criteria:

- Individuals aged between 18 and 35 years.(10)
- History of at least one significant ankle sprain with persistent symptoms of instability.(21)
- Diagnosed Functional Ankle Instability (FAI) based on the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool (CAIT) score < 24(22)
- Person is able to participate in exercise sessions and provide consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Acute ankle injury within the past six weeks.(23)
- Previous ankle surgery or fracture.(24)
- Neurological or vestibular disorders affecting balance.(25)
- Systemic conditions that limit physical activity (e.g., diabetes, arthritis).(26)

Then participants were randomly assigned into two groups using a simple randomization technique (lottery method):

- **Group A:** Isokinetic Exercise Training
- **Group B:** TheraBand Strength Training

Then participants wasundergo a 6-week supervised training program, three sessions per week. Each session waslast approximately 30–40 minutes and wasfollow the prescribed protocol for their respective group. Attendance was monitored, and participants was instructed to report any discomfort or adverse effects. After completing the 6-week intervention, the post intervention assessments was conducted using some tools (CAIT, FAAM, and NPRS) by a unaware assessor. This ensures neutral comparison of pre- and post-training outcomes.

Consort flow chart

The following CONSORT flowchart provides the participant flow throughout the study ‘Comparative Effect of Isokinetic Exercise and TheraBand Strength Training in Patients with Ankle Instability’.

Figure 1: CONSORT Flow Diagram showing the flow of participants through each stage of the randomized trial.

Results:

This study involving 60 participants (mean age 27.03 ± 5.33 years) was conducted to evaluate Isokinetic versus Thera band plus strength interventions using non-parametric tests because of non-normal baseline data. Statistically significant within-group improvements demonstrated by the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test for all participants across CAIT, NPRS, Biodex, and SEBT scores post-treatment ($p < 0.01$), shows diminish pain and improve ankle stability and balance. No significant baseline differences except for NPRS were shown by inter-group analysis using the Mann-Whitney Test but post-treatment the Isokinetic group exhibited significantly better results than the Thera band plus strength group on all measures: Post-CAIT ($p = 0.044$), Post-NPRS ($p = 0.003$), Post-Biodex ($p = 0.008$), and Post-SEBT ($p = 0.001$). These findings show that while both treatments were effective, isokinetic training results in superior enhancement in pain, ankle stability, and dynamic balance.

Table 1: Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality for Baseline Variables

Shapiro-Wilk	Statistic	Statistic	df	Sig.
BaselineCAIT	.132	.926	60	.001
BaselineNPRS	.156	.907	60	.000
BaselineBiodex	.090	.951	60	.018
BaselineSEBT	.125	.954	60	.023

Table shows the results of the Shapiro-Wilk test used to evaluate normality of baseline outcome measures for 60 participants. The Shapiro-Wilk test shows that all baseline variables were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$). Specifically, Baseline CAIT (Statistic = 0.926, $p = 0.001$), Baseline NPRS (Statistic = 0.907, $p < 0.001$), Baseline Biodex (Statistic = 0.951, $p = 0.018$), and Baseline SEBT (Statistic = 0.954, $p = 0.023$) all had p-values less than 0.05. Since the assumption of normality was broken for all baseline variables, non-parametric statistical tests were regarded proper for subsequent analysis of these measures.

Table 2: Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test – intraGroup Analysis

Within group analysis	Mean	Std. Deviation	Z	P value
BaselineCAIT	16.13	3.951	-6.755 ^b	<0.01
PostCAIT	21.95	4.696		
BaselineNPRS	6.10	1.298	-	<0.01
PostNPRS	3.10	1.526		
			6.779 ^c	
BaselineBiodex	2.7372	.70724	-6.736 ^c	<0.01
PostBiodex	1.8202	.79452		
BaselineSEBT	73.72	6.717	-	<0.01
PostSEBT	85.38	8.207		
			6.736 ^c	

Table shows the results of the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test comparing baseline and post-treatment scores for all 60 participants. For the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool (CAIT), scores significantly enhanced from a baseline mean of 16.13 ± 3.95 to 21.95 ± 4.70 post-treatment ($Z = -6.755$, $p < 0.01$). Pain intensity on the

Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) significantly lessen from 6.10 ± 1.30 at baseline to 3.10 ± 1.53 post-treatment ($Z = -6.779, p < 0.01$). Biodex balance scores showed a significant lessen from 2.74 ± 0.71 at baseline to 1.82 ± 0.79 post-intervention ($Z = -6.736, p < 0.01$), showing improved postural stability. Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT) scores significantly enhance from 73.72 ± 6.72 at baseline to 85.38 ± 8.21 post-intervention ($Z = -6.736, p < 0.01$). The results demonstrate statistically significant intra-group enhancement across all outcome measures following intervention.

Table 3: Mann-Whitney Test - interGroups Analysis for Isokinetic vs Theraband plus strength Groups

Between groups analysis		Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	P value
BaselineCAIT	Isokinetic	27.90	837.00	-1.158	.247
	theraband plus strength	33.10	993.00		
PostCAIT	Isokinetic	35.03	1051.00	-2.017	.044
	theraband plus strength	25.97	779.00		
BaselineNPRS	Isokinetic	35.62	1068.50	-2.326	.020
	theraband plus strength	25.38	761.50		
PostNPRS	Isokinetic	23.88	716.50	-3.003	.003
	theraband plus strength	37.12	1113.50		
BaselineBiodex	Isokinetic	31.42	942.50	-.407	.684
	theraband plus strength	29.58	887.50		
PostBiodex	Isokinetic	24.53	736.00	-2.647	.008
	theraband plus strength	36.47	1094.00		
BaselineSEBT	Isokinetic	30.43	913.00	-.030	.976
	theraband plus strength	30.57	917.00		
PostSEBT	Isokinetic	37.93	1138.00	-3.301	.001
	theraband plus strength	23.07	692.00		

Table shows the results of the Mann-Whitney Test comparing the Isokinetic group and Theraband plus strength group across baseline and post-intervention measures. At baseline, no statistically significant dissimilarity between groups for CAIT ($Z = -1.158, p = 0.247$), Biodex ($Z = -0.407, p = 0.684$), and SEBT ($Z = -0.030, p = 0.976$) were observed. However, Baseline NPRS was significantly difference between groups ($Z = -2.326, p = 0.020$), with the Isokinetic group showing a superior mean rank (35.62) than the Theraband plus strength group (25.38). Post-intervention, statistically significant dissimilarity were observed between groups for all outcome measures. The Isokinetic group demonstrated significantly better outcomes with enhanced Post-CAIT scores (Mean Rank = 35.03 vs 25.97; $Z = -2.017, p = 0.044$), lesser Post-NPRS scores (Mean Rank = 23.88 vs 37.12; $Z = -3.003, p = 0.003$), lesser Post-Biodex scores showing better balance (Mean Rank = 24.53 vs 36.47; $Z = -2.647, p = 0.008$), and enhanced Post-SEBT scores (Mean Rank = 37.93 vs 23.07; $Z = -3.301, p = 0.001$). These results show that the Isokinetic intervention produced significantly greater enhancements in ankle stability, pain, and dynamic balance compared to the Theraband plus strength

intervention.

Discussion

The current randomized controlled trial evaluated the comparative effectiveness of isokinetic exercise and Theraband combined with conventional strength training in individuals with ankle instability. These results indicate that although both interventions produced statistically significant improvements within groups in pain (NPRS), functional ankle stability (CAIT), balance (Biodex), and dynamic postural control (SEBT), the isokinetic training resulted in noticeably better outcomes across all post-treatment measures. These findings focused the role of exercise specificity, neuromuscular coordination, and controlled resistance training in managing ankle instability, and they align with recent evidence reported over the last five years. The notable improvement seen within both groups supports the well-established role of exercise therapy in managing CAI. Proprioception, muscle strength, and joint stability have been improved by different exercise interventions, whether resistance-based or neuromuscular-focused. (31)

In a recent study, it was found by Dos Santos et al. (2020) that structured rehabilitation programs are effective in improving the functional outcomes and decrease the recurrence of ankle sprains. Similarly, in a systematic review, it was reported by Powden et al. (2021) that noticeable improvements in CAI patients are shown by both strength training and balance-based interventions. The current study aligns with these findings, proving that even Theraband combined with strengthening exercises can have a better effect on ankle stability and pain. However, the good results observed in the isokinetic group showed that all exercise methods are not equally effective. Isokinetic training, accounting for resistance throughout the full range of motion at constant speed, allows for better muscle activation and joint control. This feature greatly contributes to the improvements seen in CAIT scores, indicating enhanced perceived ankle stability. Upholding, Gonzalez-Rave et al. (2022) indicates that isokinetic training greatly improved muscle strength and joint stability in lower limb injuries compared to traditional resistance training. They mostly focus on controlled velocity and resistance, which can better target neuromuscular problems related to instability. NPRS are used to measure the pain that is greater in the isokinetic group despite a higher pain level. This indicates strong therapeutic effects of isokinetic exercise. This showed strong therapeutic effects of isokinetic exercise. Isokinetic exercise enhanced muscle support and reduced pain or abnormal stress on ligaments. (32)

Lopez Valenciano et al. mostly focused on dynamic stabilizers of the ankle, which can decrease the nociceptive input and improve functional results. While Theraband exercises also reduce pain, their resistance is variable and may not provide controlled loading as isokinetic devices. This difference may account for the greater pain reduction observed in the isokinetic group. The findings related to balance, as assessed by Biodex scores, further support the effectiveness of isokinetic training. Balance problems cause the chronic ankle instability that is closely related to impaired proprioception and neuromuscular control. The significant improvement in the isokinetic group is consistent with Kim et al. (2021), who reported that proprioceptive response and postural stability increase by isokinetic exercises more effectively than elastic resistance exercises. Motor learning and coordination are improved by constant speed and resistance in isokinetic exercises, leading to improved balance outcomes. (33)

In contrast, Theraband and strength training are effective, but do not cause neuromuscular adaptation. Hoch et al. (2022) shows that strength is improved by elastic resistance training, but this training has a minimal effect on dynamic balance as compared to technology-assisted approaches. This is in line with the present study, where the Theraband group showed improvements but did not produce the same effects observed in the isokinetic group. By using SEBT, dynamic balance is measured by using SEBT and showed the most visible difference between groups, like the isokinetic group, which shows higher post-intervention scores. SEBT is a sensitive measure of functional stability and neuromuscular control, especially in athletic populations. (34)

These findings are supported by Clark et al. (2020), who reported that SEBT performance is improved by

controlled and multi directional movement . Isokinetic training, prepare individuals for dynamic tasks by targeting muscles at full range of motion as compared to Theraband exercises, which are often more linear and less controlled. Another important factor to consider is the role of muscle strength in ankle stability. Isokinetic training allows improve concentric and eccentric muscle actions by allow the accurate measurement and progression .Dervišević et al. (2023) showed that recurrent ankle sprains is prevented by ecentric strenght gain. The isokinetic device supports eccentric training , which shows better functional results ,observed in this study.(35)

Conclusion

In conclusion, the recent study provides strong evidence that while both interventions combined with strength training are effective in improving pain, ankle stability, and dynamic balance in patients with ankle instability, isokinetic training offers greater advantages.

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